
Technological Transformation and Territorial Inequality in Urban Peripheries: The Case of Culiacán in the Context of 5.0 Society and 5.0 Industry

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ABSTRACT: This article reflects on the impact of Late Modern Labor Society, 5.0 Society and 5.0 Industry in urban communities on the periphery of Culiacán Rosales, Sinaloa, México. This research identifies trends, causes and consequences of territorial exclusion associated with the technology gap and urban fragmentation from a systematic revision of scientific literature. The methodological approach is qualitative, exploratory-descriptive type. Results revealed structural limitations for the integration of these communities in socio-technological development processes. The concept “intelligent peripheral community” is proposed as a framework for moving forward to more inclusive urban models. This study provides a critical and contextualized view about the link between technology, territory and inequity in the field of urban development.

KEYWORDS: 5.0 Society, 5.0 Industry, urban periphery, territorial exclusion, inclusive urban development.

INTRODUCTION

Recent transformations in work dynamics, urbanization and technological development have generated profound repercussions in peripheral urban communities, particularly in Latin American contexts, marked by structural inequity. In this scenario, Culiacán Rosales city, Sinaloa, offers a paradigmatic case for analyzing how the logic imposed by Late Modern Labor Society, as well as the 5.0 Society and 5.0 Industry emergent paradigms affect territorial organization, opportunities access and quality of life in peripheral communities. This article focuses on the fields of urban economy, territorial development and social and technological innovation studies, addressing an issue that deserves to be carefully analyzed from an interdisciplinary, critical and situated perspective.

Recent literature has pointed out the contradictory effects of accelerated modernization processes in urban peripheries. On one side, a rhetoric of efficiency, connectivity and technological sustainability is being promoted; on other side, socio-economic divides, territorial fragmentation and social exclusion become more acute. Authors such as Lefebvre (1973, 1976, 1978), Castells (2010), and Bauman (2002) have warned that contemporaneous global urbanization is configured as a force that, rather than integrating, tends to make peripheral communities invisible in the development logic that is focused on commercial exploitation of urban space. In parallel, promises of 5.0 Society and 5.0 Industry –which propose harmonic integration between human and technological– important obstacles are faced when confronted with territorial realities marked by poverty, informality and lack of effective participation in the urban planning processes.

From this critical perspective, the aim of this research is to identify and describe tendencies, causes and visible consequences of the impact of the logic imposed by Late Modern Labor Society, 5.0 Society and 5.0 Industry in peripheral urban communities in the city of Culiacán Rosales, Sinaloa, with the objective of generating a framework of ideas that allow to reduce the breach between urban and peripheral management models. This proposal, stems from the systematic revision of scientific literature, doctoral theses and institutional policies, which allows to comprehend the novelty of the adopted approach: integrate the technological dimension with human condition and sustainability principles as axes for transitioning towards a fairer and more inclusive urban development model.

In terms of contributions to the disciplinary field, this research contributes to consolidate a territorial analysis approach which recognizes the need for differentiated governance models for urban peripheries. Against dominant frameworks focused on an intelligent city and competitive urban development, a perspective that proposes community resilience, social capital and social participation as foundations is proposed. In this way, it is sought to enrich current academic discussions on the impact of new socio-technical configurations of territories excluded from the hegemonic urban project.

The structure of this article is organized as follows: the first section describes the utilized methodology, based on an exploratory-descriptive approach with a systematic second source review; in the second section main findings are analyzed, grouped around three analytical axes: 5.0 Society, 5.0 Industry and sustainable urban development models. In the third section results are discussed

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under the light of contemporaneous critical theories on the late modernity, urban margination and processes of subjectivation. Finally, the conclusions show the main findings of the research and propose future lines of research which allow to advance towards a configuration of integral, human and sustainable urban and peripheral management models.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Structural transformations fueled by the transition towards Late Modern Labor Society, 5.0 Society and 5.0 Industry, constitute one of the most discussed issues in the territorial development field, urban sociology and contemporaneous politic economy. This transition raises profound questions about the role of peripheral urban communities in new sociotechnical development models. According to Beck (1992), late modernity is characterized by a transition from a production logic to a risk management logic, where economic and technologic rationalization processes tend to intensify social and spatial inequalities, particularly in urban peripheries. In the urban field, authors such as Lefebvre (1973, 1976, 1978) warns about an urban revolution promoted by advanced capitalism, which implies not only supremacy of the city over countryside, but a global restructuring of geographic space, under spatial urbanization processes. This phenomenon has led to an “implosion-explosion” of cities, marked by inequalities in access to urban areas and by the systematic exclusion of peripheries in the urban life configuration. As Díaz (2006) points out, these dynamics stem from socio-spatial fragmentation which erodes community liaisons and weakens urban identity of inhabitants of the periphery.

Recent literature has also identified the roll of emerging technologies as a problem in the redefinition of work and urban life. In this sense, the proposed 5.0 Society, initially proposed by the Japanese government (Cabinet Office, 2015), offers a vision of technological development focused on the human being, aiming to integrate cyberspace with physical space to solve structural social problems. In the same manner, 5.0 Industry positions itself as an alternative for exclusively productivist approaches, by prioritizing sustainability, resilience and wellbeing of the worker (Comisión Europea, 2021; García-Contreras & Mendoza-Hernández, 2023). Nevertheless, diverse investigations coincide in pointing out that the benefits of these models are not always equitably distributed. Latin-American critic literature, echoing ideas from authors such as Zelman (2001), Cota (2002) and Lander (2000), has shown that local governance structures, real estate market dynamics and business organization are configured in an exclusive form, reproducing approaches that systematically marginalize peripheral communities. These communities, as described by Pérez Peñuelas and Jiménez Huerta (2020), confront material as well as symbolic limitations, manifested in their scarce access to urban assets, their low participation in planning processes and the territorial stigmatization that they experience.

Furthermore, current forms of urban governance, influenced by the logic of market, tend to prioritize capitalization of urban space over social inclusion (Galli, 2008; Hardt & Negri, 2000). This situation becomes more acute in contexts such as the one in Culiacán Rosales, where the absence of urban and peripheral management integrating models has resulted in the consolidation of an excluding territorial order, that hampers the creation of a sustainable and inclusive development.

In this context, the concept of city and intelligent peripheral community emerges as a theoretical and practical alternative that seeks to articulate sustainability, technology and citizen participation. From a systematic perspective, it is proposed a management model that recognizes particularities of peripheral communities and, instead of subordinating them to an urban center logic, to grant them a protagonist role in the transition towards new forms of territorial and productive organization (Müller, 2020; Kasinathan et al., 2022).

Finally, contemporaneous debate about the implications of 5.0 Society and 5.0 Industry has begun to focus on the need for developing local strategies of adaptation and resilience. As Castells (2010), Woolcock (2001) and Matsumoto & Hwang (2020) warn, the key for the success of these models depends on their ability to incorporate local knowledge, strengthen community social capital and to design inclusive public policies, capable of responding to specific needs of peripheral urban communities.

METHODOLOGY

This research was carried out with an exploratory-descriptive type qualitative approach, oriented to identify, characterize and interpret the main trends, structural factors and territorial effects, associated to the impact of Late Modern Labor Society, 5.0 Society and 5.0 Industry on peripheral urban communities in Culiacán Rosales, Sinaloa. This methodologic design, suitable for contexts of low empiric systematization and high social complexity, allowed to build a preliminary theoretical-contextual platform that articulates global debates about urban technification and territorial exclusion with specific local realities.

On the basis of documental analysis and systematic specialized scientific literature review, key analytical categories that lay the foundations for the development of future greater empiric depth research were defined, potentially replicable in other urban contexts that confront similar inequity dynamics, special fragmentation and backlog in technological appropriation processes.

Methodological design

The methodological design of this research was structured in two complementary and interdependent phases, oriented to build a robust analytical frame which allowed to critically examine the interaction between global technological transformations and localized peripheral urban realities.

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- Phase 1: Systematic review of specialized literature. A rigorous process of search, selection and secondary sources analysis, using thematic and temporal criteria which ensure pertinence and a current documentary corpus. The review included indexed scientific articles, doctoral thesis, technical reports, books and academic research, from national as well as international origin. The objective was to identify the main theoretical approaches, empirical findings and lines of argument around four analytical dimensions: (i) Late Modern Labor Society; (ii) 5.0 Society; (iii) 5.0 Industry; and (iv) structural challenges of peripheral urban communities in contexts of high territorial inequity.
- Phase 2: Analysis thematic matrix construction. Based on bibliographic review input, a conceptual categorization matrix was developed, oriented for systematization and organization of findings in regard of key categories such as territorial exclusion, technological breach, community resilience, social capital, urban governance and alternative models for peripheral development. This tool allowed to establish analytical reports between theoretical formulas and observed concrete dynamics in the case of Culiacán Rosales, Sinaloa, providing a contextualized and critical reading of the studied phenomenon.

The utilized design fostered a comparative approach that, while centered in a specific case study, can be useful for analogous investigations in other intermediate Latin-American cities which experience similar processes of urban fragmentation, unequal technification and territorial exclusion.

Procedure

The documental research was carried out in academic databases of renowned prestige —such as Scopus, RedALyC, SciELO and Google Scholar— through the use of combined strategies of key words. These combinations allowed to enhance the thematic specter, incorporating interdisciplinary perspectives that are linked to urban studies, critical sociology, technological innovation and territorial planning.

In order to ensure quality and relevance of the documentary corpus, rigorous inclusion criteria were established: thematic pertinence concerning the study in question at present days (with emphasis in publications after the year 2010), methodological soundness and recognition in the corresponding field of discipline. Documents without peer review, opinion articles and texts without substantial analytical elements were expressly excluded.

The process culminated with the selection of 53 documents that were systematically analyzed and classified in the constructed thematic matrix. This classification allowed to identify argumentative patterns, theoretical gaps and critical convergence areas between different reviewed approaches. In addition, it made possible to establish a comparative base between urban contexts, emphasizing the specificities of the case in Culiacán Rosales in regard of observed trends in other Latin-American cities with similar peripheral urbanization trajectories.

Ethical criteria and validation

Although this research did not involve field work neither direct interaction with human subjects nor compilation of personal or sensitive data, fundamental ethical principles governing responsible academic production were rigorously observed. In particular, transparency in the methodological procedures was guaranteed, traceability and verifiability of utilized sources, as well as the integrity and intellectual honesty in the interpretation of the findings.

With the objective of strengthening internal validation of the research and minimizing interpretation biases, an analytical triangulation strategy which integrated three complementary dimensions was implemented: (i) a systematic specialized scientific literature review; (ii) a critical contrast with contemporaneous theoretical frames originated from different disciplines (urban sociology, technological research, territorial economy); and (iii) incorporation of contextual data concerning urban and social configuration in the municipality of Culiacán Rosales, extracted from trustworthy and renowned secondary sources, such as Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Geografía (INEGI), Instituto Municipal de Planeación (IMPLAN) and ONU-Hábitat program.

This approach contributed to create a robust analysis, based on the articulation between contextual empirical evidence, multidisciplinary theoretical substantiation and aligned ethical criteria with social science comparative scientific research.

LIMITATIONS

It is recognized that being an exploratory research, exclusively based on secondary sources, the presented findings have a predominantly interpretative nature and, therefore, are not susceptible to statistical generalization. However, this limitation does not undermine its analytical worth. On the contrary, developed critical systematization contributes to the consolidation of a preliminary conceptual framework with high heuristic potential, capable of guiding future empirical research—of qualitative, quantitative or mixed type— concerning socio territorial transformation processes in peripheral urban contexts.

In particular, the contributions of this research allow to problematize the applicability and the differential effects of 5.0 Society and 5.0 Industry paradigms in structurally unequal territories, offering a comparative and contextualized approach that can be extrapolated, with due adaptations, to other urban realities. In this way, this work provides solid theoretical and methodological

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foundations for designing deeper investigation which integrate field work, empirical validation and direct participation from community actors.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Specialized literature analysis allowed to identify convergent patterns relative to the differentiated impact that Late Modern Labor Society, 5.0 Society and 5.0 Industry exert on peripheral urban communities, particularly in the case of Culiacán Rosales, Sinaloa. Contrary to technocratic speeches that promote these paradigms as neutral mechanisms of progress, the findings reveal a series of structural effects that, far from shrinking gaps, tend to exacerbate pre-existent socio-spatial asymmetries.

In this framework, three interrelated analytical dimensions are distinguished: (1) the persistence of structural challenges associated with historic territorial marginalization of urban peripheries; (2) the widening of the technological gap and the consolidation of new forms of functional fragmentation of urban space; and (3) the critical conditions —yet in construction— that would allow to advance towards intelligent urban models that prioritize sustainability, equity and the centrality of the human person. These categories allow the comparison of global regulatory frameworks with local realities, and highlight the need for approaches which are more integrating, contextualized and participative in order to understand and transform peripheries to move into the digital era.

Structural challenges in the urban periphery.

Analysis revealed that peripheral urban communities, as Culiacán Rosales, confront a structural configuration of cumulative disadvantage, resulting from historical processes of territorial marginalization, institutional weakness and systematic precarious working conditions. These conditions are expressed in multiple dimensions: fragmentation of urban tissue, unequal access to services and infrastructure, and scarce participation in the decision-making concerning territory use and management.

As shown in Chart 1, qualitative indicators reveal a structural exclusion that exceeds economy and reaches symbolic, politic and spatial dimensions.

This phenomenon is not exclusive to the context of Sinaloa; comparative studies in Latin-American cities like Bogotá, Lima or São Paulo have documented similar patterns of urban marginalization, in which periphery is treated as an externality of metropolitan growth. According to Lefebvre (1973, 1978), it is reaffirmed that modern cities do not necessarily integrate, but produce differentiated territorialities, functionally subordinated to the central core. For his part, Díaz (2006) suggests that these peripheries are the result of urban planning, oriented by a market logic which exclude large sectors of the population from the effective right to the city.

This situation leads to a structural cycle of urban inequality reproduction, where exclusion from access to urban-technologic development is not a collateral consequence, but an inherent condition of the dominant urban model. Hence, the analysis of these challenges allows to comprehend how the implementation of paradigms like 5.0 Society or 5.0 Industry could, if not corrected this basic condition, exacerbate instead of narrowing the existent gaps.

Table 1. Indicators of structural exclusion in peripheral urban communities

Indicator	Description
Socio spatial fragmentation	Presence of popular urbanization without functional nor symbolic integration to the rest of the city
Unequal access to infrastructure	Limited access to basic services, deficient public transportation and precarious technologic connectivity
Marginalization of urban design	Scarce or non-existent participation in processes of planification and regulation of territorial development
Weak community social capital	Erosion of support networks, weakening of collective identity and low territorial cohesion

Technological breach and functional fragmentation of territory.

Analysis reveals a marked disparity in access, use and appropriation of digital technology between the central urban core and peripheral communities of Culiacán Rosales. Despite of the optimistic speech that accompanies 5.0 Society and 5.0 Industry — focused on inclusive digitalization and human well-being—, peripheries face structural obstacles that hinder their effective incorporation to these processes. Among the main identified challenges are: low connectivity coverage, limited digital literacy and scarce integration of these communities into urban technological innovation strategies.

This pattern is not exclusive of the mexican case. In cities like Medellín, Buenos Aires or Ciudad de Guatemala, recent studies have documented how the expansion of intelligent infrastructures tend to concentrate in central or high real estate value areas, reproducing a logic of territorial digital exclusion. As pointed out by Kasinathan et al. (2022) and Matsumoto (2020), the implementation of emergent technologies in unequal contexts, without strategies for differentiated inclusion, not only fails in reducing existent breaches, but can also enhance them, further displacing historically marginalized sectors.

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The lack of focused public policies, with territorial perspective and intersectional approach, constitutes a critical obstacle for peripheral communities to significantly integrate to urban-technological development processes. This institutional deficit prevents such populations to actively participate in the configuration of a sustainable urban model which is resilient and truly centered in collective well-being. In this context, the digital breach must be understood not only as a technical matter, but as a material expression of structural inequalities that pervade the territory and citizens.

Table 2. Indicators of technological breach in peripheral communities in Culiacán

Indicator	Estimated value / observed situation	Reference source
Access to landline internet	Inferior to 55 % in peripheral areas	INEGI (2020); estimaciones IMPLAN
Population with basic digital skills	Inferior to 35 %	Encuesta Nacional sobre Disponibilidad y Uso de TIC (2021)
Technological equipment at home	Low possession rate of computers, printers and tablets	INEGI (2020)
Inclusion in policies of an intelligent city	Limited or inexistent	Revisión documental (2024)

Conditions for the transition into intelligent peripheral communities.

Against the background of structural exclusion and diagnosed technological breach, the study identifies a set of critical conditions that must prevail in order for an effective transition to take place towards a more equitable and inclusive urban development model. This model is conceptualized within the approach of intelligent peripheral community, understood not as a simple extension of traditional intelligent cities, but as an alternative paradigm that articulates technology, sustainability, territorial justice and citizen participation from the peripheral environmental specificities.

Contrary to conventional models of smart cities — frequently focused on operative efficiency, big data and investment attraction —, the concept here proposed emphasizes the generation of local capabilities, the community resilience and the collaborative governance as fundamental bases for a structural transformation with a territorial approach. In this context, there are five interdependent axes for the configuration of these communities: (1) digital inclusion with rights approach; (2) context adapted sustainable infrastructure; (3) social capital strengthening and community networks; (4) effective participation in planning processes and public decision making; and (5) intersectorial and intercultural governance models.

This approach is in striking contradiction to the experiences in cities, where deployment of urban intelligent technologies has been strongly linked to mercantilizing of space and planning technocratization. However, emergent experiences in Medellín (Colombia), Quito (Ecuador) and Recife (Brasil) show that territorial inclusion based approaches and community ownership of technology can generate more sustainable and equitable results when aligned with participative planning and spatial justice processes.

Nevertheless, findings also reveal that the transition towards this model confronts serious obstacles, prominent amongst them are: institutional fragmentation of urban policies, systematic exclusion of the peripheries in decision making processes and the absence of multiscale planning schemes with differential approach. Overcoming these barriers requires not only political willingness, but a profound redesign of regulatory frameworks and territorial management instruments, in order to place peripheral communities at the center of the urban transformation agenda in the era of 5.0 Society and 5.0 Industry.

Table 3. Key elements for the consolidation of intelligent peripheral communities

Dimension	Requisitos fundamentales
Human	Recognition of the dignity, capabilities and rights of peripheral population
Technological	Equal access to digital structure, connectivity and technological literacy
Institutional	Reforms in urban planning that integrate peripheral territories
Social	Strengthening social capital and community networks
Environmental	Sustainability strategies adapted to local context

Critical resignification of urban periphery: towards an inclusive territorial governance

The results obtained in this research offer substantial evidence which supports a structural critic of hegemonic urbanization models, characterized by their excluding socio-spatial inequality reproducing logic. In the case of intermediate cities such as Culiacán, these models manifest themselves in an urban-functional configuration that concentrates infrastructure, services and opportunities in central areas, while maintaining peripheries in structural subordinated conditions, as well as material and symbolic.

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Although technological transformations linked to 5.0 Society and 5.0 Industry open possibilities for redefining parameters of urban development, their democratizing capability finds itself severely limited by an institutional architecture that prioritizes technocratic efficiency over territorial equality. In this context, peripheries not only are excluded from the design of public policies, but also are made invisible as legitimate spaces of innovation, social reproduction and politics agency.

This problematic is not exclusive of the Mexican case, diverse studies on Latin-American cities —such as Santiago de Chile, Ciudad de México or Belo Horizonte— document similar patterns, in which neoliberal urbanism has promoted a mercantile vision of space that strengthens territorial fragmentation and limits the right to the city for wide population sectors.

In the perspectives of Castells (2010) and Hardt & Negri (2000), this work claims that the transformation of contemporaneous urban order requires a strategic reevaluation of peripheries, this redefinition implies recognizing them not as residual areas nor simple receptors of mitigation policies, but territories with their own productive organizational and creative capabilities. In consequence, urgent need for reorienting public policies towards a logic of inclusive territorial governance that incorporates effective mechanisms of participation, recognition and redistribution, and that allows peripheral communities to constitute as fundamental actors in socio-territorial innovation processes and the construction of fairer, resilient and resilient cities.

CONCLUSIONS

This article addressed the challenges, visible implications and impacts imposed by the Late Modern Labor Society, 5.0 Society and 5.0 Industry about peripheral urban communities in the city Culiacán Rosales, Sinaloa. Throughout the text, an interdisciplinary theoretical frame was developed, based on classic and contemporaneous authors of urban theory, critical sociology and technological studies; it was applied an explanatory-descriptive qualitative methodology, based on systematic review of scientific literature; and organized results are presented in three thematic axes: the structural challenges of urban periphery, the technological breach and the conditions for a transition towards intelligent peripheral communities.

Among the most relevant contributions of this research on the field of urban economy, territorial development and studies about technological governance, there are:

- The identification of a structural breach between the dominant urban management models and the real conditions of peripheral communities, examining their exclusion from the potential benefits that are promised by paradigms of 5.0 Society and 5.0 Industry.
- The conceptual proposal of “intelligent peripheral community” as analytic category and practical guidance for thinking in alternatives of technological integration, sustainability and citizen participation from the periphery, not as a subordinate territory, but as a strategic actor in the construction of inclusive cities.
- The critical articulation between transformations of work, urban spatial reconfiguration and the new forms of exclusion, indicating how the technological advances can exacerbate inequalities if they are not accompanied by inclusive public policies and planning approaches that recognize territorial diversity.

Despite its relevance, this research presents certain limitations, mainly related to its exploratory nature and the secondary character of the utilized data. Field work was not carried out, nor direct testimony of community actors incorporated, which restricts empirical validation of some approaches. Furthermore, while a contextualized approach was used in the case of Culiacán, the findings could be enriched by means of comparative studies with other Latin-American cities with similar urban dynamics.

In this context, the next future lines of research are proposed:

- The realization of mixed methodologies case studies that incorporate participative research techniques with habitants of peripheral communities.
- Analysis of local public policies, especially in the fields of transport, housing, digital connectivity and economic development, to evaluate its alignment or discrepancy with the principles of 5.0 Society and 5.0 Industry.
- The exploration of institutional mechanisms of collaborative governance which allow peripheral communities to actively have an impact in urban planning and intelligent landscape design.
- The validation of the concept: intelligent peripheral community through territorial, social and technological indicators that allow to measure its viability and evolution in different urban contexts.

In sum, this research constitutes an effort to link Latin-American critical thinking with the global debate about technology, territory and urban exclusion, proposing an integrating approach which places human condition as the main axis of every sociotechnical transformation. The task ahead is to build real bridges – not metaphorical – between innovation and territorial equity, between urban development and peripheral dignity.

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